

ASSAULT AND MARRIAGE STABILITY: ANALYSIS OF INTIMATE PARTNER VIOLENCE IN UYO METROPOLIS, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to investigate Assault and Marriage Stability in the Uyo metropolis of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Social Control Theory was adopted by the researcher for the study. Four research questions were also formulated for the study, from which a questionnaire was constructed and used to collect data. 398 study participants were engaged through the distribution of questionnaires to randomly selected study respondents in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The collected data were analysed descriptively using statement tables. Findings of the study revealed that there great impact of unconscious, physical assault, intimidation, and humiliation by intimate partners on family stability among the Uyo metropolis of Akwa Ibom State. The researcher recommended that, among others, the state government should see how to enforce punishment by the law against assault of any type that occurs from an intimate relationship and people, especially the young ones should be careful of who they give to in intimate relationship to avoid abuse.

Keywords: Assault, marriage stability, Social Control, and Uyo

INTRODUCTION

Intimate partner violence (IPV) is frequently occurring in every nation of the earth, irrespective of social, economic, religious or cultural group, and it is being witnessed by people of the world daily as reported by the media. Although women can be violent in relationships with men, and violence is also sometimes found in same-sex partnerships, the overwhelming burden of partner violence is borne by women at the hands of men worldwide (WHO, 2012). There has been a perception that domestic violence occurs only in socially disadvantaged families in our modern society, but research has shown that domestic violence occurs in all sectors of society, regardless of cultural, religious, social, legal, and economic

aspects (AlMajali andAlsrehan, 2019).

Patrilineal influence of the society has contributed to the increasing number of intimate partner violence (IPV), and such actions have in so many ways affected children's psychological development through various levels of abuse (Al Majali and Alsrehan, 2019). When a mother is abused, the child who is closer to the mother than the father does feel abuse psychologically. Al Majali and Alsrehan (2019) posit that violence, especially that happens between father and mother, causes disorders which affect all levels of a child's personality development (Daniel and Peters, 2024), especially his/her emotional and cognitive spheres, as well as behaviour.

Marriage is an institution in this modern-day society that is undergoing significant changes across the world (Bassey et al., 2023). In most societies today, several factors contributing to trends that are seen in present-day marital relationships include changing roles for men and women brought about by the women's movement, which advocates for role equality, as well as more demanding economic times, which have led to violence among couples (Hamel, 1993). Apart from modern-day societal influences which are affecting the structure of marriage relationships, people's expectations of marriage are changing, and partners are often sought out based on the desire for companionship and personal fulfilment rather than solely for purposes of procreation (Hamel, 1993). Different forms of violence have forced the changing faces of marriage structure in the world today, despite the huge bride prices involved (Paul and Peters, 2023). The most disturbing trend in marriage is seen in the rising divorce rate across the world, which is affecting marital stability across developed and developing nations of the world, and affects life expectancy among women (Ben, Daniel and Peters, 2023).

Intimate partner violence (IPV) has taken many forms, like rapes, physical assault, intimidation, constant belittling and humiliation (National Centre for Injury Prevention and Control, 2003). The fact that women are often emotionally involved with and economically dependent on those who victimise them has major implications for both the dynamics of abuse and the approaches to dealing with intimate partner violence (IPV). Intimate partner violence is not a social problem that is restricted to one ethnic group in Sub-Saharan Africa. It has been a general problem across the various ethnic and social groups across the continent of Africa. In the Uyo metropolis of the Niger Delta region, intimate partner violence is growing as society becomes more complex with an accompanied shift in the cultural context of marriage. This is the area of gap which this social research work seeks to fill (Hamel, 1993).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) can be committed by both men and women, regardless of whether the relationships are marital, heterosexual, or homosexual (Anderson, 2002). Violence against women represents a significant public health issue globally today. Evidence from the criminal justice system, hospital and medical records, mental health documentation, social services, and surveys in the United States indicates that thousands of women sustain injuries or are killed annually due to violence, often by someone with whom they have had or currently have an intimate relationship. Nearly one-third of female homicide victims recorded by police are murdered by an intimate partner (National Centre for Injury Prevention and Control, 2003). Women have endured various forms of violence from intimate partners at different levels, with some records indicating that lives have been lost as a result (Hamel, 1993).

Uyo metropolis is recognised for its cultural marriage practices that promote marital stability. This is supported by the high regard given to married couples through traditional marriage customs in Uyo metropolis in line with the state's traditional marriage practice. In the traditional Ibibio society, marriage was viewed as a sacred institution accompanied by specific taboos, where both men and women were expected to hold their spouses and their marriage in high esteem. Polygamy was practised within this cultural context to alleviate the burden on one woman as a wife, who was seen as responsible for numerous marital and conjugal duties, necessitating assistance from another woman, rather than facing abuse. However, the cultural transformation in the traditional setting of Uyo metropolis today, influenced by modernisation and globalisation, has led to a transition from marital stability to instability, significantly impacting the family structure and stability within the society, which child labour becomes one of the resultant effects (Peters and Bassey, 2023).

Currently, the sanctity associated with marriage as an institution among the residents of Uyo metropolis is rapidly diminishing, leading many couples to view marriage not as a collective commitment but rather as a pursuit of individual interests (National Centre for Injury Prevention and Control, 2003). This pursuit of personal gain has resulted in intimate partner violence (IPV) across various types of intimate relationships, adversely impacting the stability of marriages in the contemporary Uyo metropolis. In light of this situation, this research aims to investigate the impact of assault as a form of intimate partner violence (IPV) on marriage stability within the Uyo metropolis of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Typology by Form of Abuse in IPV

One method of categorising IPV is based on the type of abuse. Gaining insight into the different forms of abuse can assist in developing strategies to address each specific type. According to the WHO (2002), IPV is divided into physical, sexual, and psychological abuse. Some policymakers have recognized additional categories, including economic and social abuse; however it remains unclear whether these subcategories truly represent distinct aspects of IPV (Hegarty, Sheehan, & Schonfeld, 1999). This classification is commonly utilized and reported in research, either as separate entities such as physical violence, psychological violence, and sexual violence, or in various combinations (Devries et al., 2013; World Health Organisation, 2013).

Physical Violence

Physical violence refers to the use of physical force to inflict pain, injury or physical suffering on the victim. Slapping, beating, kicking, pinching, biting, pushing, shoving, dragging, stabbing, spanking, scratching, hitting with a fist or something else that could hurt, burning, choking, threatening or using a gun, knife, or any other weapon are some examples of physical violence (García-Moreno, Jansen, Ellsberg, Heise, & Watts, 2005).

Sexual Violence

Sexual violence encompasses “any sexual act, attempt to obtain a sexual act, unwanted sexual comments or advances, or acts to traffic, or otherwise directed, against a person's sexuality using coercion, by any person, regardless of their relationship to the victim, in any setting, including but not limited to home and work” (Jewkes, Sen, & Garcia-Moreno, 2002). In the context of IPV, sexual abuse refers to physically forcing a partner to

have sexual intercourse, who did not want it, forcing a partner to do something that she found degrading or humiliating (García-Moreno et al., 2005), harming her during sex or forcing her to have sex without protection (World Health Organisation, 2014).

Psychological Violence

Psychological violence encompasses a range of behaviours aimed at humiliating and controlling another person, whether in public or private settings. Instances of psychological violence include verbal abuse, name-calling, persistent criticism, blackmail, actions or statements designed to induce embarrassment, threats of physical harm towards women or children, surveillance and limitation of movements, curtailing access to friends and family, hindering economic independence, and restricting access to information, assistance, or essential services such as education and healthcare (Follingstad & DeHart, 2000; WHO, 2002).

Typology by Type of Violence in IPV

Kelly and Johnson (2008) maintain that IPV is not a unitary phenomenon and that different types of partner violence are apparent in different contexts, samples, and methodologies. Among various typologies offered by type of violence, the most widely used include Johnson's (1995) and Johnston's (1993) typology.

Johnson's Typology

Michael Johnson, an American sociologist, has been working on the typology of violence since early 1990s and over time, and with colleagues, he has developed and refined his proposed typology (Johnson, 1995; Johnson, 2008; Kelly & Johnson, 2008). His work has been identified as the most influential of the typologies proposed so far (Anderson, 2009; Langhinrichsen-Rohling, 2010). Johnson maintains that the perspective of both feminist and family researchers can be appropriate in explaining IPV. The feminist perspective identifies violence as a tactic used by men to control and dominate their partner within a heterosexual relationship; whereas, researchers from the family perspective maintain that IPV is an outcome of the conflict in couples and can be present in both heterosexual and same-sex relationships. In addition, from the family perspective, women can also perpetrate violence against their male partners (Straus, 2006). Johnson (1995) initially proposed two forms of IPV, patriarchal terrorism, and common couple violence.

The typology, since then, has been expanded and according to Johnson and colleagues (Abbott et al., 1995; Johnson, 2000; Johnson & Ferraro, 2000; Kelly & Johnson, 2008), IPV can be classified into five qualitatively different types. These include Coercive Controlling Violence (CCV), Violent Resistance, Situational Couple Violence (SCV), Mutual Violent Control Violence, and Separation-Instigated Violence (Beck et al., 2013). The distinctions in these types were not based on a single incident, but a general pattern of control in the relationship between intimate partners (Johnson & Ferraro, 2000).

Coercive Controlling Violence (CCV)

CCV refers to a pattern of emotionally abusive intimidation, coercion, and control combined with physical violence perpetrated against an intimate partner (Kelly & Johnson, 2008). It refers to a pattern of control and manipulation by a partner against their intimate partner. A person controls their spouse's actions, relationships, and activities. The coercive

partner keeps the victim under surveillance, and failure to follow the rules established by them often results in punitive action (Beck et al., 2013; Kelly & Johnson, 2008; Tanha, Beck, Figueredo, & Raghavan, 2009). Major forms of violence, as shown in the power and control wheel, include intimidation, emotional abuse, isolation, minimising, denying, and blaming, use of children, asserting male privilege, economic abuse, and coercion and threats (Pence & Paymar, 1993). Johnson maintains that the abuser may use one or a combination of several tactics to keep the victim under control.

Johnson (1995) initially used the term 'Patriarchal Terrorism' for this type of violence. The next term used was 'Intimate Terrorism,' and that was later changed to Coercive Controlling Violence (CCV). This type of violence is more severe, occurs more frequently and escalates over time (Johnson & Leone, 2005; Kelly & Johnson, 2008; Leone, Johnson, Cohan, & Lloyd, 2004). CCV is the type of IPV that is most frequently encountered in agency settings, such as law enforcement, the courts, shelters, and hospitals (Kelly & Johnson, 2008). In heterosexual relationships, CCV is most often perpetrated by men. Johnson (2006), for instance, found that 97% of the CCV in the Pittsburgh sample were male-perpetrated, while Graham-Kevan & Archer (2003) reported that 87% of CCV in their British sample was male-perpetrated. Existence of male perpetration of CCV was also supported by recent studies (Ansara & Hindin, 2009, 2011; Beck et al., 2013; Gulliver & Fanslow, 2015). Little systematic research has been undertaken on women's use of CCV, but some studies have identified women as perpetrators of this type of violence in both heterosexual and same-sex relationships (Beck et al., 2013; Hines, Brown, & Dunning, 2007; Migliaccio, 2002; Renzetti, 1992).

Violent Resistance

This refers to the type of violence used by the victim of violence to resist violence from a coercive, controlling partner. Various terms that have been used to describe this type of violence include Female Resistance, Resistive/Reactive Violence and Self-Defense (Beck et al., 2013; Kelly & Johnson, 2008). Feminist researchers consider all types of violence perpetrated by women against their male partners as a form of female resistance and, therefore, use the term battered women syndrome (Johnson, 1995).

However, unlike feminist researchers, Johnson acknowledges that violence can be perpetrated by women against their intimate partners and suggests that the term violence resistance, better reflects the fact that a man or woman can resort to violence in an attempt to stop the violence or to stand up for themselves (Kelly & Johnson, 2008). Women's Violent Resistance rarely leads to encounters with law enforcement due to its short-lived nature. For many women, resorting to self-protective violence may be almost automatic and emerge as soon as the coercively controlling and violent partner begins to use violence. However, in heterosexual relationships, most women find out quickly that responding with violence is ineffective and may in fact, make the situation worse (Johnson, 2008). For example, the using data from the National Crime Victimization Survey, Johnson (2010) indicate that women who defend themselves against attacks from their intimate partners are twice as likely to sustain injury as those who do not. Though much research has been conducted to explore the violent resistive behaviour of females, particularly women who murder their intimate partners (Kelly & Johnson, 2008), research on men's resistive behaviour is still limited.

Situational Couple Violence (SCV)

The SCV is defined as the type of violence between partners when an individual can be violent and non-controlling in a relationship with a nonviolent partner or a violent but non-controlling partner (Johnson, 2006). It is the most common type of violence in the general population and can be perpetrated by men or women against their partner. The intention behind this type of violence is not power, control or coercion; it arises from situations, arguments and conflicts between partners, which then escalate into physical violence (Kelly & Johnson, 2008). This results from one or both partners' inability to manage conflict or anger (Johnson, 2006). The frequency and intensity of violence tend not to increase over time and usually involve minor forms of violence compared with CCV.

SCV may encompass verbally abusive acts such as cursing, shouting, name-calling, and accusations of infidelity. However, it does not have a chronic pattern of controlling, intimidating, and stalking behaviours, which is a characteristic of CCV (Kelly & Johnson, 2008). This type of violence was initially named Common Couple Violence, and terms such as Male-Controlling Interactive Violence, and Conflict Motivated Violence (Ellis & Stuckless, 2006) have also been used to refer to this type of violence (Kelly & Johnson, 2008).

Large general population-based studies indicate that SCV is initiated at similar rates by men and women. For instance, Straus (2006) found male rates of violence toward a partner of 12.2% and female rates of 12.4%. In a survey of cohabiting and married respondents, males reported one-year rates of male-to-female violence of 12.9% and female respondents reported female-to-male violence of 12.5% (Kwong, Bartholomew, & Dutton, 1999).

Mutual Violent Control Violence

This type of violence occurs when both partners are violent and controlling towards each other (i.e., two intimate terrorists) (Beck et al., 2013). It is this type of violence, which supports the notion of gender symmetry in the phenomenon of IPV. It is considered a rare type of violence and little is known about its features, frequency and consequences (Johnson, 2000; Johnson & Ferraro, 2000; Kelly & Johnson, 2008). Consistent with this finding, only four percent of the sample in a recent study was identified under this category (Beck et al., 2013). However, in a recent study, 70% (n=624) of the sample was identified as mutually violent (WHO, 2010).

Separation-Instigated

Violence Separation-Instigated Violence occurs in couples who are in the process of separation and divorce (Johnston & Campbell, 1993). Such couples do not normally have a history of violence in their intimate relationship and the violent episodes are triggered in response to traumatic experiences at the time of separation. Such experiences include finding the home empty after the spouse's (and perhaps, children's) departure, humiliation and insult faced as a result of separation and divorce (especially if the person is a known figure), and allegations of sexual abuse (Johnston & Campbell, 1993). The violence in such situation, represents an atypical and serious loss of psychological control that is sometimes also described as 'just going nuts'. Such violence is typically limited to one or two mild to more severe forms of violence episodes during the separation period (Kelly & Johnson, 2008, p. 487). Seen symmetrically in both men and women, this type of violence is more likely to be perpetrated by the spouse who has been left and/or is shocked by divorce action. The various

ways a person may react include lashing out, throwing objects at the spouse, destroying property and trying to intimidate the spouse or her new partner through various actions such as sideswiping (to strike along the side in passing) or damaging their car (Kelly & Johnson, 2008).

As mentioned previously, the Johnson's focus is not the seriousness or frequency of violence, but in the presence or absence of control (Johnson & Leone, 2005), though physical violence is present in all five types. Johnson (1993) tested his theory by conducting a secondary analysis of the 'Pittsburgh data' composed of community and clinical (court and shelter) samples. The findings revealed that men and women in the community sample were more likely to use SCV (86% of the cases), when men and women were compared in the clinical samples. Johnson's typology has been supported by some researchers (Ansara & Hindin, 2009, 2011; Beck et al., 2013; Frye, Manganello, Pence & Dasgupta, 2006).

However, there has been some criticism of Johnson's typology and its various aspects. Further research to test Johnson's typology is recommended (Beck et al., 2013; Gulliver & Fanslow, 2015; Hines & Douglas, 2010). Johnston's Typology Janet Johnston and colleagues attempted to differentiate types of IPV in the context of custody and access disputes (Johnston & Campbell, 1993). The authors studied divorcing parents involved in disputes over parenting following relationship breakdown in two different research studies involving 80 parents and 100 children in one study and 60 parents and 75 children in another. The authors derived five types of IPV on the basis of three primary motivations for the use of violence. These included ongoing and episodic male battering, female initiated violence, separation-engendered violence, male-controlling interactive violence, and violence due to psychotic and paranoid reactions (Johnston & Campbell, 1993). There are similarities and overlaps in the work of Michael Johnson and Janet Johnston. Episodic Male Battering Episodic male battering, as the name suggests, is initiated by men against their partner and may be present in up to 18% of high-conflict divorcing families (Johnston & Campbell, 1993). It is similar to CCV identified by Johnson (Kelly & Johnson, 2008). Female initiated violence may be present in 15% of high-conflict divorcing families. Moderately severe violence can occur if the perpetrator loses control while restraining the attacking spouse (Johnston & Campbell, 1993).

Separation-Engendered Violence

Separation-engendered violence occurs only during or after the separation period with no violence during the marriage itself. It can be present in up to 25% of high-conflict divorcing families. The physical violence is generally initiated by the partner who feels deserted and this can be either the man or the woman (Johnston & Campbell, 1993). This is similar to Kelly and Johnson's (2008) separation-instigated violence. Male controlling interactive violence arises from mutual verbal arguments and insults progressing to physical struggles. It can be seen in up to 20% of high-conflict divorcing families.

Violence can be initiated by either partner; however, the man may physically dominate or overpower the woman. In addition, a woman's struggles and counterattacks may result in the man becoming more dangerous and threatening (Johnston & Campbell, 1993). This type of violence is similar to SCV (Kelly & Johnson, 2008). Psychotic and Paranoid Reactions Finally, psychotic and paranoid reactions are a result of disordered thinking and paranoia. They can be present in up to 65% of high conflict divorcing families (Johnston & Campbell, 1993).

Consequences of Intimate Partner Violence

According to WHO (2012), IPV affects women's physical and mental health through direct pathways such as injury, and indirect pathways such as chronic health problems, that arise from prolonged stress. A history of experiencing violence is therefore a risk factor for many diseases and conditions. Current research suggests that the influence of abuse can persist long after the violence has stopped. The more severe the abuse, the greater its impact on a woman's physical and mental health, and the impact over time of different types and multiple episodes of abuse appears to be cumulative (WHO, 2012).

Injury and physical health

According to WHO (2012), the physical damage resulting from IPV can include: bruises and welts; lacerations and abrasions; abdominal or thoracic injuries; fractures and broken bones or teeth; sight and hearing damage; head injury; attempted strangulation; and back and neck injury. However, in addition to injury, and possibly far more common, are ailments that often have no identifiable medical cause, or are difficult to diagnose. These are sometimes referred to as 'functional disorders' or 'stress-related conditions', and include irritable bowel syndrome/gastrointestinal symptoms, fibromyalgia, various chronic pain syndromes and exacerbation of asthma (WHO, 2012).

In the WHO multi-country study, the prevalence of injury among women who had ever been physically abused by their partner ranged from 19% in Ethiopia to 55% in Peru. Abused women were also twice as likely as non-abused women to report poor health and physical and mental health problems, even if the violence occurred years before (WHO, 2012).

Mental health and suicide

Evidence suggests that women who their partners abuse suffer higher levels of depression, anxiety and phobias than non-abused women. In the WHO multi-country study, reports of emotional distress, thoughts of suicide, and attempted suicide were significantly higher among women who had ever experienced physical or sexual violence than those who had not (WHO, 2012). In addition, IPV has also been linked with: alcohol and drug abuse; eating and sleep disorders; physical inactivity; poor self-esteem; post-traumatic stress disorder; smoking; self-harm; and unsafe sexual behaviour.

Sexual and reproductive health

IPV may lead to a host of negative sexual and reproductive health consequences for women, including unintended and unwanted pregnancy, abortion and unsafe abortion, sexually transmitted infections including HIV, pregnancy complications, pelvic inflammatory disease, urinary tract infections and sexual dysfunction. IPV can have a direct effect on women's sexual and reproductive health, such as sexually transmitted infections through forced sexual intercourse within marriage, or through indirect pathways, for example, by making it difficult for women to negotiate contraceptive or condom use with their partner (WHO, 2012).

Violence during pregnancy studies has found substantial levels of physical IPV during pregnancy in settings around the world (WHO, 2012). The WHO multi-country study found prevalence of physical IPV in pregnancy ranging from 1% in urban Japan to 28% in

provincial Peru, with prevalence in most sites of 4–12%. Similarly, a review of studies from 19 countries found prevalence ranging from 2% in settings such as Australia, Denmark and Cambodia, to 13.5% in Uganda, with the majority ranging between 4% and 9%. A few facility-based studies in some settings have found even higher prevalence, including one from Egypt with an estimated prevalence of 32% and a review of studies from Africa that found prevalence as high as 40% in some settings. Violence during pregnancy has been associated with: miscarriage; late entry into prenatal care; stillbirth; premature labour and birth; fatal injury; and low-birth-weight or small-for-gestational-age infants. IPV may also account for a proportion of maternal mortality, although this association is often unrecognized by policy-makers (WHO, 2012).

Homicide and other mortality

Studies from a range of countries have found that 40–70% of female murder victims were killed by their husband or boyfriend, often in the context of an abusive relationship. In addition, evidence suggests that IPV increases the risk of a woman committing suicide, and may also increase the risk of contracting HIV, and thus of AIDS-related death (WHO, 2012).

Effects on children

Many studies have found an association between IPV against women and negative social and health consequences for children, including anxiety, depression, poor school performance and negative health outcomes. A large body of evidence indicates that exposure to IPV against the mother is one of the most common factors associated with male perpetration and female experience of IPV later in life. Several studies have found an association between IPV and child abuse within the same household. In addition, studies from some low-income countries, including Nicaragua and Bangladesh have found that children whose mothers were abused are less likely to be immunised, have higher rates of diarrhoeal disease, and/or are at greater risk of dying before the age of five (WHO, 2012).

Best Approaches to Preventing and Responding to IPV

According to WHO (2012), several international reviews in recent years have synthesised evidence on effective, or at least promising, approaches to preventing and responding to violence against women, including IPV. There a need for comprehensive, multi-sectoral, long-term collaboration between governments and civil society at all levels of the ecological framework. Unfortunately, while individual-level interventions are relatively easy to assess, evaluating comprehensive, multi-level, multi-component programmes and institution-wide reforms is more challenging; as a result, these approaches are almost certainly the key to long-term prevention but are also the most under-researched (WHO, 2012).

However, there has been an identification of a set of specific strategies that have demonstrated promise or effectiveness which include: reform civil and criminal legal frameworks; organize media and advocacy campaigns to raise awareness about existing legislation; strengthen women's civil rights related to divorce, property, child support and custody; build coalitions of government and civil society institutions; build the evidence base for advocacy and awareness; use behaviour change communication to achieve social change; transform whole institutions in every sector, using a gender perspective; in particular, integrate attention to violence against women into sexual and reproductive health services;

promote social and economic empowerment of women and girls; build comprehensive service responses to IPV survivors in communities; design life-skills and school-based programmes; engage men and boys to promote nonviolence and gender equality; and provide early-intervention services to at-risk families (WHO, 2012).

Many initiatives have aimed to influence knowledge, attitudes and behaviours of young people through life-skills programmes in low-income countries or classroom-based dating violence prevention programmes in the USA, such as Safe Dates, which demonstrated effectiveness in reducing perpetration (WHO, 2012).

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Social Control Theory

Social control theory proposes that people's relationships, commitments, values, norms, and beliefs encourage them not to break the law (*Ngo Mitchell, 2009*). Thus, if moral codes are internalized and individuals are tied into and have a stake in their wider community, they will voluntarily limit their propensity to commit deviant acts. The theory seeks to understand the ways in which it is possible to reduce the likelihood of criminality developing in individuals. It does not consider motivational issues, simply stating that human beings may choose to engage in a wide range of activities, unless the range is limited by the processes of socialisation and social learning. The theory derives from a Hobbesian view of human nature as represented in *Leviathan*, i.e. that all choices are constrained by implicit social contracts, agreements and arrangements among people. Thus, morality is created in the construction of social order, assigning costs and consequences to certain choices and defining some as evil, immoral and/or illegal (*Ngo Mitchell, 2009*).

The theory is adopted by the researcher to explain the subject matter of the study which indicates that IPV is an extension of certain level of social control exercise by a partner over his or her partner through relationships, commitments, values, norms, and beliefs. The theory is also adopted to explain that IPV being a deviant behaviour can be control through relationships, commitments, values, norms, and beliefs which will encourage them not to break the law.

METHODOLOGY

This study examined the effect of assault as an intimate partner violence (IPV) in marriage stability among the Uyo metropolis of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It sets out to examine the relationship between chosen variables using the survey method. Survey research method was adopted for this study because the research study covers a large population and a complex study area. Simple random sampling method was used for the purposes of selecting study participants. The researchers engaged both secondary and primary data for this study.

The study area was Uyo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom state. Uyo local government area is situated in Akwa Ibom state which is in the South-south geopolitical division of Nigeria. The headquarters of the Local Government Area are in the town of Nnung Udoe Ibesikpo while the area is bordered by the Uruan, Nsit Atai, Etinan, Nsit Ibom, and Uyo Local Government Areas. Uyo comprises of several towns and villages such as Ikot Nko, Akpa Utong, Ikot Atang uma, Ikot Edium, Ikot Itok, Obio Aduang, Ntuk Otong, and Aba Ukpo. The Ibibio language is widely spoken in Uyo Local Government Area while Christianity is the extensively practiced religion in the Local Government Area. Popular

festivals held in Uyo Local Government Area include the Ekong and the Usoro Ekpo festivals while notable landmarks in the area include the Mount Carmel General Hospital (manpower.com, 2022).

The targeted population of this study was the estimated population of Uyo LGA which is 79,656 inhabitants with the area being majorly populated by the Uyo metropolis (manpower.com, 2022). In determining the sample size, the researcher used Alien Taro Yamane method. Yamane (1967) provides a simplified formula to calculate sample size. The formula was used to calculate the sample size for this study and is shown below. A 95% confidence level and level of maximum variability ($P= 0.5$) was assumed. Where n is the sample size, N is the population size (834,039), and e is the level of precision (allowable error) that is 5% or 0.05. Therefore, the sample size of this study was 398, and the respondents were randomly selected from 3 communities; 1 from Asutan clan, 1 from Ibesikpo clan and Nunng Udoe the local government headquarters of Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State.

The data for this study were obtained from two sources, primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected through the use of questionnaire administered to respondents by the researcher. Questionnaire was adopted as tool for data collection because it provided closed-ended options that were easy to choose by the respondents. The researcher also obtained secondary data from existing sources such as books, journals, and the internet. Data for this study were collected by the researchers. In the process of data collection, the study respondents were met at their residences, offices and shops respectively. To have the respondents co-operate with the researcher, began by disclosing the objectives of the study to the respondents and requested their candid responses as they fill the questionnaire. The instrument used in this study was the questionnaire. The questionnaire contained questions that assessed the background characteristics of the respondent as well as questions that required candid opinion of the respondent on the subject matter. The questionnaire contained closed ended questions which sought to collect information on the opinion of the respondents. The data collected in this study were analysed descriptively using simple percentage method. Charts are also used for data analysis through application of Microsoft Office 2010 application package.

RESULT

Impact of Physical Assault by IPV on Family Stability

Table 1: **Impact of physical assault by intimate partners on family stability**

Physical Assault by intimate partners and family stability	Yes	No
Partners take beating up other partners in intimate relationships as means of resolving problems	220	178
Men are fun of beating women in intimate relationships	205	193
Women are fun of beating men in intimate relationships	121	277
Children are in some cases beaten by partners as a result of problems in relationships	297	101
Some partners injure other partners in intimate relationship	277	121

Source: Researchers' Field Work (2025)

The analysis of Table 1 shows that on the opinion that partners take beating up other partners in intimate relationships as means of resolving problems, 220 were of “Yes” while 178 were of the opinions “No”. On the opinion that most men are fun of beating women in intimate relationships, 205 were of yes and 193 were of no. On the opinion that women are

fun of beating men in intimate relationships, 121 were of yes and 277 were of the no. On the opinion that children are in some cases beaten by partners as a result of problems in relationships, 297 respondents were of the yes while 101 respondents were of the no. On the last opinion which states that some partners injure other partners in intimate relationship, 277 respondents were of the yes while 121 were of the no opinion.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study sought to examine how physical assault affects marriages in Uyo metropolis, in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The analysis of the statement table shows that there is a great impact of physical assault by intimate partners on family stability. This emerged from the responses of the study respondents who accepted the statements in favour of the result that most IPV are usually assaulted. This finding is in agreement with WHO (2012). According to WHO (2012), the physical damage resulting from IPV can include: bruises and welts; lacerations and abrasions; abdominal or thoracic injuries; fractures and broken bones or teeth; sight and hearing damage; head injury; attempted strangulation; and back and neck injury. Conclusively, the findings of the study in accordance to the research question and objective show that physical assault as intimate partners violence (IPV) has a great influence on family stability among the people of Uyo metropolis in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Assault as IPV has great effects on physical, mental, health, and psychological aspects of the victims, especially among women.

CONCLUSION

In this study, data were collected and analysed descriptively through the use of statement tables. The study sought to examine how physical assault affects marriages in Uyo metropolis, in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, and revealed that unconscious physical assault is part of the violence experienced by victims of intimate partner violence (IPV), especially among the young women of the Uyo metropolis in Akwa Ibom State. These findings imply that this violence affects family stability among the Uyo metropolis of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of findings and conclusions of the study, the researchers make the following recommendations;

1. People especially the young ones should be careful of who they give into for marital relationship to avoid abuse.
2. Government should see how to enforce punishment by the law against assault of any type that occurs from intimate relationship.
3. Non-governmental organisations and religious bodies should see how to offer educative activities for young couples

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